

СТАРТАП ПРОЕКТЫ – КАК СПОСОБ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ИНТЕРЕСА ОБУЧАЮЩИХСЯ К ФИЗИКЕ

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STARTUP PROJECTS AS A WAY TO INCREASE STUDENTS' INTEREST IN PHYSICS

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Аннотация

В настоящее время в образовательном процессе наблюдается низкий интерес обучающихся к естественным дисциплинам, в том числе к физике. В этом случае задействовано несколько факторов. Например, когда обучающиеся считают физику самой сложной наукой, неправильно используют методы и приемы в процессе обучения и т.д. Учителя, применяя различные подходы к обучению, борются с указанной проблемой. Однако мы также не можем сказать, что проблема имеет целостное решение. В этой статье мы сможем получить ответы на вопросы, как пробудить интерес обучающихся к физике, какой подход более эффективен.

Abstract

Currently, there is a low interest of students in the educational process in natural disciplines, including physics. In this case several factors are involved. For example, when students consider physics to be the most difficult science, improperly use methods and techniques in the learning process, etc. Teachers, using different approaches to teaching, are struggling with the above problem. However, we also cannot say that the problem has a holistic solution. In this article we can get answers to the questions how to arouse students' interest in physics, which approach is more effective.

Ключевые слова: интересы обучающихся, факторы, повышение интереса, стартап проект, физика.

Keywords: student interests, factors, increasing interest, startup project, physics.

Interest can be seen as a means and a goal of educational processes. There are several theoretical views and assumptions about "interest". As for the conceptualization of the psychological structure of "interest", it is divided into two main areas of research. First, interest is interpreted as a personality trait, that is, as a permanent preference for a certain area of knowledge or activity. This is called personal interest. Second, interest is interpreted as a situation related to a certain attraction of a particular situation. This is called situational interest. The inherent personal interest persists over time and can be divided into latent and renewed interest. Personal interest develops slowly and tends to have a lasting effect on a person's knowledge and values. And situational interest is assumed to be spontaneous, fleeting and common between people. Situational interest is directly related to an emotional situation. It arises suddenly because of something in close proximity and can have a short-term impact on a

person's knowledge and values. It also arises as a function of other people's interest.

The aspect of situational interest can be distinguished as follows:

- 1) interest in a particular topic in physics (e.g., optics);
- 2) interest in a certain context presented in that topic (e.g., an optical device used every day);
- 3) interest in a particular activity that is allowed to be pursued depending on that topic and context (e.g., building a simple but functional telescope).

Based on the research, we can say that it is important to make learning content meaningful and personal for students. In this case, students' emotional reactions to learning and learning material are also relevant, which allows the development of situational interest of students. Teachers can facilitate the transition of situational interest to personal interest by selecting content, context, and teaching methods. This oncogenic transformation is a two-step mental process

in which internal and identification play a central role. The first step is to elicit or reinforce situational interest. That is, the variables that initially stimulated students' interest in a particular topic. Situational interest of learners to transition to personal interest, there must be learning conditions that make the content of learning meaningful and personally meaningful to learners. The second step is an internal process in which situational interest can become a personal or personal interest. Thus, motivation and interest are no longer viewed as separate variables. This is why it is important for the teacher to know what content and context the students are interested in. Thus, interest can be viewed as an integrated component of an interconnected network of mental, social, and physical factors in a particular learning situation. It seems logical that learning content is related to students' interest. However, this is not always a necessary strategy; there are times when learners need to master basic skills that they are not interested in. [1, p.161]

There are various factors that affect students' interest in physics. Students' underachievement in physics may be due to both internal and external factors. Internal factors include the student's attitude, motivation, interests, knowledge, skills, hopes, assumptions, and goals. External factors-state of the learner's learning environment, such as teachers' use of teaching methods, family environment, etc.

In addition, because many students consider physics to be the most difficult science, their level of interest in physics declines before they start school. As a factor of influence, we can say that most of all science courses in high school are based on a large amount of memory. That is, it is possible to memorize the theoretical information of science by heart during instruction, but the same theory cannot be applied in practice. As a result, the lack of practice and the abundance of theoretical data reduces interest in physics. In addition, students who are very proficient in science courses, including chemistry, biology, etc., acquire a high level of learning and cognitive skills. However, when using reading skills, it is important to pay attention to the difference between chemistry, biology, etc. courses and physics courses. Although the pattern in a chemistry course is similar to a physics course, the concepts may differ. Students think they have mastered a chemistry course as well as a physics course, and then it doesn't materialize. Then interest in physics decreases dramatically because of the extreme level of difficulty that students associate with physics. This is also one of the influencing factors.

Several studies have identified gender, personality traits, structural variables, and curriculum variables as a number of factors that influence students' attitudes toward science in science. The most important of these is gender. Research by some scientists has shown that women have more positive attitudes toward science than men, with a relatively high interest in science. However, statistically significant gender differences have not been proven. Unfortunately, these less favorable male attitudes often lead to a decreased interest in science. In this regard, students' study habits, attitudes, and interest in physics were found to be the

best predictors of their performance in physics. And it has been suggested that student gender has no effect on student performance .[2, p.152]

One of the factors reducing the level of students' interest in the physics subject is the complexity of theoretical information and information in the physics course. However, according to the results of special research and observations, the background theoretical information aimed at achieving the physics course does not affect the interest of students in physics lessons. On the contrary, there was an opinion that the reference theoretical information helps students to form an idea about the work of scientists to achieve scientific progress, about the hardworking individuals who fought to bring science to a new level. In addition, it increased students' interest not only in physics, but also in other natural sciences; their basic scientific concepts improved their memory skills and improved their ability to solve complex problems.

To increase students' interest in physics, the teacher faces a number of challenges. It is determined by each teacher, focusing on his or her personality. That is, determines an effective approach to awaken or increase the interest of students, taking into account their age characteristics, level of learning, etc. In this regard, teachers can define an effective approach by solving a number of problems. For example, to increase students' interest in physics, we can identify at least four physics teacher problems related to the development of the curriculum and textbooks.

The first challenge is to assume that learners are interested in the context in which the theories and practices of physical science are discussed in everyday life. The content being studied in physics enters into a creative or exploratory context, e.g., a skill that can be learned and the content of physics are related to each other. Here, the connection between the exploratory content and the skills to be learned is purely voluntary. For example, a physics teacher might follow a creative or exploratory course and explain how paranormal phenomena have been studied or what the origin of electromagnetic waves is.

The second challenge is to explain how to increase the content and context of high school physics. If meaningful physics theories and practices are taught in the context of another topic, rather than being limited to one topic, there will be an opportunity to increase students' interest in physics content. There is a wide range of topics that can be approached in a different context of another topic. For example, a discussion of satellite and space exploration seems like an interesting topic for students if it is taught on the basis of mechanics, electromagnetic radiation, and nuclear fusion.

A third challenge is to incorporate examples of everyday life, health knowledge, and life sciences into the teaching of physics. These can be phenomena that can be related to, or directly related to, specific contexts of interest to students. For example, the use of animals and plants that students see in everyday life, sports or hobbies, and the environment. Some physical concepts can be used in the context of certain information about animals and plants (mass, weight, volume, acceleration,

speed, kinetic energy, etc.) instead of various physical tools.

The fourth challenge is learning – based technology. It is important for all students to find universal approaches to demonstrate the interest and importance of a technical application. Everyone uses technical applications, so user-friendly testing and user-centered design might be an interesting context. In addition, an intervention study of student motivation and physics learning in a context that combines a technological context with a human or astronomical context would be helpful. A good example of integrating the human context with the technological context can be seen in many physics textbooks for high school students. These topics help students both understand human attitudes toward technology and see the importance of technology in our daily lives. Thus, schools have great potential to change the way technology is taught. We conclude that creating a classroom environment that enhances students' STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) career intentions can increase their interest and increase or maintain their performance in physics. [3, p.281]

In enhancing students' interest in physics, each teacher can apply and suggest an effective approach according to his/her observation, research work. For example, an innovative and effective approach to the use of startup projects in the teaching process to arouse students' interest in physics and enhance their creativity. Startup projects help students to develop creative thinking and improve their research skills.[4, p.5]

To make the subject of physics and its instructional materials interesting, teachers should offer students meaningful choices, use well-organized texts, choose understandable texts, use texts that students know or should know, encourage students to be active, and give appropriate advice. You should also consider the following guidelines when teaching physics:

- opportunity for choice;
- correlation of theoretical content with students' previous experience;
- practical work in accordance with the theory;
- stimulate discussion and reflection on the social significance of science;
- presenting physics content in applied contexts;
- demonstrating physics as it relates to human life;

There are the following methods that have proven effective in increasing students' motivation and their interest and desire to learn physics.

Firstly, create a positive atmosphere in the classroom. A special "climate" in the classroom affects the effectiveness of learning, the interest of the students.

Secondly, it is necessary to give choices. Once students have acquired some skills or become familiar with some content, there is always an opportunity to offer the student a choice. Giving students choices is crucial to increasing their engagement. For physics content, learners should be given choices between choosing answer questions or writing definitions and doing research papers and problem solving that will

give them better control over the learning process to increase learner engagement and interest.

Third, true learning. Students are more engaged when they feel that the topic they are learning relates to extracurricular life. The basic idea is that students are more interested in showing the real life context of what they are learning, equipping them with practical and useful skills, and touching on topics related to their extracurricular lives.

Fourth, the use of project-based learning. The project-based learning process occurs when students begin with a problem to solve, complete an investigation, and then solve the problem using the tools and information you normally teach in multiple classrooms.

Fifth, you need to define learning objectives. Because of the amount of information and data, some topics can be overwhelming. You need to define specific learning objectives that will show students exactly what they need to learn. This helps eliminate some of the problems that students experience when learning a new topic.

Sixth, making interdisciplinary connections. Sometimes students do not see how what they are learning in one discipline matches up with what they are learning in other disciplines. Interdisciplinary connections can give students a sense of context while increasing their interest in physics.

Seventh, students need to be shown how they can use what they have learned in physics in the future. Some students may not like this because they don't see the point of what they are reading. The most common theme among students is: "why should I know this?" Instead of waiting for them to ask this question, why not include it in the lesson plans you do. The lesson plan template should include how students can use this information in the future. Then explain it to the students during the lesson.

Eighth, providing motivation to learn. Incentives and praise can be anything from leisure time at the end of the lesson. Explain to students exactly what they need to do to receive praise. [5, p.740]

Ninth, apply hands-on learning and add support materials. Well-designed hands-on activities guide students into the world around them, sparking their interest and guiding them through engaging experiences. When students can participate in a variety of experiments, the information they learn can make sense and be of great interest in physics.

Consistent with the issues discussed above, it is concluded that teachers can develop students' situational interest in personal interest by combining the three-dimensional aspects of interest, such as content (topics), context, and learning activities with content and context. Lack of student interest can be a serious problem for teachers, which they need to address using strategies such as using technology-based learning in physics, using project-based learning, making interdisciplinary connections, and demonstrating the use of physics concepts in the future. Adapting the curriculum by incorporating topics of interest to students can be a very effective tool for addressing some of the pressing challenges of physics

education. If the new science and technology curriculum is to be successful in improving students' scientific literacy and interest in physics, this deficiency must be considered and overcome.

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APPLICATION OF ACTIVE TEACHING METHODS IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

In the article the necessity of application of active learning methods and the influence of teaching methods on results of training of specialists in higher educational institutions. Choosing a method of teaching, the teacher takes into account the time allotted for the study of this topic, as well as the importance of educational material for further professional or educational activities of the student. But we must remember that learning is not only the assimilation of knowledge and skills, but also the development, education of students. The objectives of training in modern conditions is not so much the mastery of knowledge and skills in the chosen specialty as the preparation of students for self-education, the development of their interest in learning and the formation of cognitive needs. Recommendations for the implementation of active methods in the educational process were proposed. Active learning methods help to achieve the goals and contribute to personal and professional growth.

Keywords: active methods, interactive methods, training, computer science, didactic tasks.

The role of education in the current period of Kazakhstan's development is determined by the tasks and requirements of the rapidly developing modern society. Current trends in educational institutions are the reason for the training of highly qualified specialists of various profiles. Today, the main task is not to give students a certain knowledge, but to influence the way of thinking and the way of looking at the phenomena. Ensuring the quality training of specialists often depends on the effectiveness of the educational process. The future specialist needs not only to have deep and flexible professional knowledge and business skills, but also to have developed professional and social qualities and characteristics. In other words, the current level of development of production directs a modern specialist to the need to master professional skills at the level of professional competence. Professional competences allow to adapt to changing conditions in the labor market.

The use of active teaching methods in the teaching of computer science teaching methodology is based on a number of reasons: firstly, students should not only acquire certain knowledge, but should be able to apply it in a real practical situation.

Active learning is, first of all, new types, methods and tools of so-called active learning. Complex and purposeful use of technical tools is of great importance in improving educational processes, but the most important thing in the educational process is the

student's activity. Active methods include all kinds of classroom lessons with students.

During the lesson, the use of methods such as «Case Method», «Business games», «round table», etc. significantly activates the educational process. These methods contribute to the active interaction of students and teachers.

In order to improve and activate the educational process in higher educational institutions, it is of great importance to know and take into account the peculiarities of education, they create the need to reconstruct the stereotypes of educational work formed at school and arm them with new business and educational-cognitive activity skills.

Scientists and methodologists, teachers such as A. Alimov, F. B. Buribekova, N. zh. Zhanatbekova, A. K. Bekbolganova and others contribute to the development of active teaching methods.

In his works, A. Alimov not only substantiated the need for the use of active methods in all types of educational work of students, but also introduced the concept of problem-dialogical learning as a complete bearer of the essence of the processes of joint activity of teachers and students, as well as their mutual activity in the framework of «subject-subjective» relations.

The use of problem-based and developmental learning in practice has led to the emergence of so-called «active» methods. The formation of active